

Actual vs Predicted (AverageUV)

Standardized Residuals (AverageUV)

Partial Regression Plot (AverageUV)

Durbin-Watson Statistic

$$DW = 1.3272$$

Interpretation:

- 1 = positive autocorrelation**
- 2 = no autocorrelation**
- 4 = negative autocorrelation**

Breusch–Pagan Test

LM Statistic: 3.1102

p-value: 0.0778

Conclusion: No Heteroskedasticity

White Test

White Statistic: 3.1878

df: 2

p-value: 0.2031

Conclusion: No Heteroskedasticity

Histogram of Residuals (AverageUV)

P-P Plot (Normality Test) – AverageUV

